

DYES DERIVED FROM ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE, PART VIII. (7-METHYL)THIONAPHTHENE- ACENAPHTHYLENE-INDIGOS

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Acenaphthenequinone and its various substituted products have been condensed with 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene and the corresponding thioindigoid vat dyes obtained. The previous method of preparation of 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene has been modified. 7:7'-Dimethylthioindigo has been obtained from 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene.

In previous parts of this series (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 682; 1936, 13, 94; 1938, 15, 23) the influence of a methyl group in the 4-, 5-, and 6-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigo (I)

was fully studied, and the variation of colour in relation to the constitution of these three classes of dyes was also established, both qualitatively and quantitatively.

With a view to completing this series, the study of the influence of a Me group in the 7-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of (I) was undertaken, and for this purpose acenaphthenequinone and its derivatives were condensed with 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 219)

The 7-methylthionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos are beautiful, red and deep red crystalline products. They develop lustre when rubbed vigorously, analogous to the 4-, 5- and 6-methyl dyes (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

The dyeing shades have been fully developed in all cases on wool from an acid bath (*cf. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 680) and also on cotton from the hydro-sulphite vat, except the methoxy derivative which offered resistance to reduction in the vat in the same manner as the methoxy compounds belonging to the 4-, 5- and 6-methyl series, 5-chloro series, and 2:3-naphthathiophene series (Guha, *loc. cit. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 710; 1939, 16, 127).

The preparation of 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene required modification as the vigorous reaction which had occurred resulted in a poor yield. The method adopted now not only increased the yield, but also gave a purer product more easily. The cause of the low melting point of the product by the previous method was found to be due to absorption of oily mother-liquor. By the oxidation of 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene, 7:7'-dimethylthioindigo (*cf. D. R. P. 241910*) was obtained for the purpose of comparing its dyeing properties with those of the three isomeric dimethylthioindigos and their parent compound (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 506).

The quantitative measurement of the depth of colour of these 7-methyl dyes (absorption curves, absorption maxima, etc.) and a discussion of the result of the comparative study of all the isomeric methylthionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos considered together, as well as of the dimethylthioindigos, will be communicated in a succeeding paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-(7-Methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigo.—When a solution of acenaphthenequinone (0'546g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0'492g) in boiling glacial acetic acid (40 c.c.) was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 cc.), a thick red crystalline mass separated. More glacial acetic acid (40 c.c.) was added and the mixture shaken well and boiled for 20 minutes. The sharp needle-shaped red product (0'825g.) was finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 304'. Separated from alcohol, it was yellowish red in colour. It dyes cotton dark red from a violet-blue hydrosulphite vat, and wool a similar shade from an acid bath. (Found : S, 9'92. $C_{21}H_{12}O_2S$ requires S, 9'75 per cent).

2-(7-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8-(3-chloro)acenaphthylene-indigo was similarly prepared from 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0'6495g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0'492g.) dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (60 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.). The thick mass of the thread-like, yellowish red needles was treated with 30 c.c. more of glacial acetic acid and boiled for 20-25 minutes, filtered and collected. The dye (0'907g.) was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in fine red needles, m. p. 274°. It dyes cotton red from a blue hydrosulphite vat, and wool yellowish red from an acid bath. (Found : Cl, 10'27. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 9'79 per cent).

2-(7-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8-(3-bromo)acenaphthylene-indigo separated from a red solution of 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0'6525g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0'41g.) in 80 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and 3 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid on heating for 20 minutes. The thread-like deep red needle-shaped substance (0'821g.) was crystallised from a large quantity of acetic acid in long fine needles, m. p. 264-65°. It dyes cotton the same shade as the chlorocompound and wool red from an acid bath. (Found : Br, 19'54. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2BrS$ requires Br, 19'65 per cent).

2-(7-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8-(1'-methoxy)acenaphthylene-indigo.—The red-brown solution obtained by dissolving β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0'636g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0'492g) in 85 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid, when treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4c.c.), turned deep red (almost black). After a short while a scarlet-red precipitate separated which was boiled for 25 minutes and collected. The dye (0'444g.) was crystallised from pyridine in fine clusters of needle, m. p. 300. It dyes cotton a faint pink shade from a bluish violet vat, and wool red from an acid bath. (Found : S, 9'1. $C_{22}H_{11}O_2S$ requires S, 8'93 per cent).

7-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene.—A solution of *o*-methylphenylthioglycollic acid (10g.), m.p. 108° (cf. Rabaut, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1902, iii, 27, 690) records

m.p. 106°) in hot, dry benzene (120-130 c.c.) was treated gradually with phosphorus pentoxide (40 g.). It was boiled on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, and left at room temperature for 48 hours. After removing benzene, the bulky blackish brown soft residue was dissolved in ice-cold aqueous alkali; the solution acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and distilled in steam. The distillate containing the colourless crystalline substance was left overnight in a cooled chamber; filtered, washed with a little cold water, and dried in a vacuum desiccator, when it turned faint pink, yield about 2 g. It was crystallised from petroleum ether in long rectangular plates, m.p. 80-81°. (Found: S, 19.37. C_9H_8OS requires S, 19.51 per cent).

7:7-Dimethylthioindigo-7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene was dissolved in the required quantity of warm dilute sodium hydroxide (2N). An aqueous solution of potassium ferricyanide (5%) was added gradually with shaking until a red precipitate was no longer formed and the solution warmed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on the water-bath. The precipitate was collected, washed well with hot water and dried. The dye was crystallised from nitrobenzene in fine dark red needles, not melting below 318°. It is soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, aniline, xylene, chloroform; difficultly soluble in benzene and carbon tetrachloride; sparingly soluble in acetic acid and alcohol. The solution of the substance in concentrated sulphuric acid is deep green; water precipitates the original substance. It dyes cotton a pleasant violet red from a light greenish yellow hydrosulphite vat, and wool dark violet-red colour from an acid bath. (Found: S, 20.13. $C_{18}H_{12}O_2S_2$ requires S, 19.75 per cent).

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